

Studies of the Chemistry of Azole Derivatives: V. New Potential Antispasmodic Thiazoles

J. M. Singh* and B. N. Tripathi

In continuation of our earlier investigations^{1,2} on azole derivatives this communication deals with the preparation of new potential antispasmodic compounds. Blicke³ reported that β -amino alkylaryl ketones with thiazolyl substituents attached to secondary amino group possessed this activity. Accordingly substituted 2-(β -benzoyl ethylamino)thiazoles, as potential antispasmodic drugs, have been prepared by condensation reaction of substituted 2-aminothiazoles with paraformaldehyde and acetophenone or *p*-bromoacetophenone.

Thiazoles having methyl-, phenyl-, 4'-bromophenyl-, 3',4'-dihydroxyphenyl- or 2,3',4'-trihydroxyphenyl group as substituent at position 4 have been employed for the reaction. The substituent having two or three hydroxy groups have been especially selected so as to give the final products having chelation characteristics, which play several different roles in the drug action⁴. (3',4'-Diacetoxyphenyl) thiazole was prepared by refluxing the hydroxy-derivative with acetic anhydride.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted 2-aminothiazoles were prepared following the procedure of Dodson and King⁵ and previously reported method¹.

2-(β -benzoyl ethylamino)-4-(3',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)thiazole.

*To whom correspondence concerning this paper should be sent :

1. J. M. Singh, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 1168.
2. S. P. Gupta and J. M. Singh, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 336.
3. F. F. Blicke, *Am. Rev. Biochem.*, 1944, **13**, 549.
4. J. Schubert, *Sci. Amer.*, 1966, **214**, No. 5, 40.
5. R. M. Dodson and L. C. King *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1945, **67**, 2242.

A mixture of 2-amino-4-(3',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)-thiazole (2 g.), acetophenone (1.9 g.), paraformaldehyde (1 g.) in ethanol (150 ml.) was refluxed for 3 hrs, (0.5 g.) of paraformaldehyde was further added and refluxing continued for 5 hrs. On concentration under reduced pressure, it afforded a pasty mass which on keeping in contact of ammonia solidified. It was then washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. Data are listed in the table. All other compounds were prepared by following this method.

Thanks are due to Dr. Kartar Singh, Director, Defence Science Laboratory and Dr. H. K. Acharya, Assistant Director for providing necessary facilities.

TABLE

Substituted 2-(β-Benzoyl ethylamino)-4-(3',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)thiazole

R	R ₁	R ₂	Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Sulphur %		Nitrogen %	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1 Phenyl	4-Bromophenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	40	175	8.3	8.29	7.45	7.23
2 <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	Phenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	45	300	8.31	8.29	7.54	7.23
3 Phenyl	Methyl	Carbethoxy	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	41	161	10.06	10.06	9.01	8.81
4 <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	-do-	-do-	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₃ S	39	185	8.1	8.01	7.31	7.05
5 Phenyl	3',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ S	45	290	9.3	9.43	8.41	8.26
6 Phenyl	3',4'-Diacetoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅ S	45	190	7.86	7.56	7.0	6.85
7 <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	3',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₃ S	50	260	7.7	7.65	7.32	6.69
8 Phenyl	2',3',4'-Trihydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	42	300	9.1	9.01	8.15	7.88
9 <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	-do-	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ BrO ₄ S	45	250	7.35	7.37	6.62	6.45

All melting points are uncorrected and ethanol was used for recrystallization.